

Literature Review: Analysis of *Soft Skills* Affecting the Recruitment Process for General Practitioners in Hospitals

Winata Fika Permata Sari¹, Winny Setyonugroho², Qurratul Aini³

^{1,2,3} Master in Hospital Administration, University of Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta, Yogyakarta

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 28 June 2022	The purpose of this system is to analyze Soft Skills that affect the recruitment process of general practitioners in hospitals. The literature review in this study was carried out through a systematic selection sought from international databases. The author searches for data sources from various databases, including PubMed (https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/), and SAGE journals (https://journals.sagepub.com/). The articles found were 10 articles that discussed the recruitment process and the influence of soft skills in the recruitment process. In the recruitment process, prospective applicants go through various recruitment and selection stages. The method used by the hospital is done online and offline. The online method is widely used in the form of information that is disseminated through the hospital web, Facebook and Instagram offline by recruiting internal hospitals such as recommendations from hospital employees and foundations. Hospitals under the auspices of the foundation prefer to use the offline method, namely by withdrawing from existing foundations, although it is possible to recruit online.
Corresponding author: Winata Fika Permata Sari	
KEYWORDS: Soft Skills, General Practitioner Recruitment	

I. PRELIMINARY

Facing increasingly high competition in the hospital industry, the hospital requires a management system that can anticipate dynamic environmental changes. The hospital, which was previously a social institution, is now developing into an increasingly competitive service industry. This condition is a major challenge for hospital management to be able to compete and survive. This has resulted in the need for qualified and competent Human Resources (HR) as one of the important components that must be managed to support the achievement of the goals expected by an organization.

Hospitals are unique organizations due to the combination of labor-intensive, capital-intensive, and technology-intensive, so that hospital management becomes a separate discipline that produces two things at once, namely technology and human behavior in an organization (Purnamasari, 2017). The core activities in the hospital itself include health services carried out by health workers, while management and technical activities that are indirectly related to health services are carried out by non-health workers.

Various studies show that health workers have an important role to improve the maximum quality of health services for the community. According to WHO, health workers contribute up to 80% in the successful achievement of health development goals. In supporting medical services in hospitals,

general practitioners play a strategic role. A general practitioner is known as a doctor at the first level of service, where general practitioners play a role in providing prevention, diagnosis, early treatment, and referring to specialists if needed. In addition, general practitioners also play an important role in providing initial and ongoing medical care to patients of all age groups.

In daily practice, doctors must be able to make diagnostic decisions related to their duties in managing patients holistically. However, it is not uncommon for doctors and other medical personnel to have different opinions regarding treatment or making the right decisions for patients. In this case, not only skilled, in addition to academic ability (hard skills), a doctor must also pay attention to abilities in several things that are inherent in a person or also known as aspects of soft skills. Hard skill is the minimum ability needed by someone to be able to work. Someone with the same level of education and experience on average has a relatively similar level of hard skills. While soft skills are abilities that are relatively invisible (intangible) and sometimes very difficult to measure. However, soft skills are also believed to be a complement to hard skills that will determine a person's success at work.

Based on the results of research conducted by Harvard University, Carnegie Foundation, and Stanford Research Center, United States that soft skills are responsible for 85% of

a person's career success, and only 15% lies in hard skills. Meanwhile, the Indonesian Ministry of National Education 2009 also stated that soft skills will determine 85% of a person's success in education. Good soft skills are needed in communication, collaboration, and cooperation between medical officers from various professions which will affect the quality of service and patient safety whose role is no less important than academic ability.

In Indonesia, the number of general practitioners continues to increase every year. This will also lead to increasingly fierce competition in the world of work. However, based on the existing reality, human resources with good soft skills tend to decline. For this reason, the performance of employees, including general practitioners who have soft skills with good qualification standards, is expected to be able to improve the quality of hospitals. These high-quality human resources will be obtained through an effective and planned recruitment process.

Recruitment is the process of searching, finding, and attracting a competent person to be employed in a company. This aims to obtain a supply of prospective applicants so that companies have a greater opportunity to make choices for prospective employees who are considered to have met the qualification standards.

The recruitment process starts from the registration of applicants to the submission of applications to related companies. After the recruitment process is carried out effectively, the employee selection process will then be carried out to select the best person to fill certain positions in accordance with the existing positions. Meanwhile, the wrong recruitment process can have a negative impact, including the emergence of labor unrest, decreased enthusiasm and enthusiasm for work, decreased employee performance, errors in carrying out tasks and lack of responsibility for tasks. This of course can damage production, customer satisfaction and service quality.

Based on the description of the background above, the authors are interested in conducting research with the title "*Analysis of Soft Skills Affecting the Recruitment Process for General Practitioners in Hospitals*"

II. METHOD

The literature review in this study was carried out by systematic selection which was traced from international databases. The author searches for data sources from various databases, including using PubMed (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/>), and SAGE journals (<https://journals.sagepub.com/>). The library search technique uses keywords that match the research questions. The list of keywords that will be used as the basis for a broader literature search is described in table 1 below:

Table 1. List of keywords and their possible synonym

Keywords	Synonym
Soft skills	Interpersonal skills Communication skills Social skills Psychosocial skill
Recruitment process	Basic Employee Recruitment Employee Resources Recruitment Methods

III. RESEARCH RESULT

Table 2. Summary of Literature Review

No.	Author Name, Year, Research Title	Research methods	Recruitment process	Soft skills
1.	Wijayanti <i>et al.</i> (2017), “ <i>Health Service Needs on Soft Skills for Graduate of Third Diploma Nursing in Indonesia</i> ”	Quantitative		Soft skills requirement Communication skills are required, namely the ability to provide clear information The attitude skill required is honesty Attitude towards the expected institution, namely loyalty Self-development needed by users is a good mastery of knowledge Skills needed to ensure patient safety The ability to make decisions is the ability to identify problems Supporting skills needed are planning work well
2	Kaseger <i>et al.</i> , (2019), “ <i>Analysis of Health Personnel Recruitment at Cantia Tompaso Baru Hospital</i> ”	Qualitative	Recruitment stages Announce publicly through social media Acceptance of application letters through the HRD. Unstructured interview Background check Interview about the personality of the prospective health worker Acceptance decision	
3	Viviyanti Azwar, (2013), “ <i>The Moderation Role of Soft Skills in Improving the Quality of Hospital Services</i> ”	Quantitative	.	The relationship between organizational resources and service quality is strengthened by soft skills Soft skills play a positive role in strengthening the relationship between organizational resources and service quality Soft skills are able to support organizational resource training so as to improve the quality of health services
4	Arifandi & Andreasta Meilala, (2017), “ <i>Factors Affecting the</i>	Qualitative	Doctor recruitment problems lack of applicants due to	

“Literature Review: Analysis of *Soft Skills* Affecting the Recruitment Process for General Practitioners in Hospitals”

No.	Author Name, Year, Research Title	Research methods	Recruitment process	Soft skills
	<i>Recruitment of Doctors at the Health Center in the Working Area of the Health Office of Buol Regency in 2016</i> ”		lack of interest and willingness of doctors to work	
5	Suryanti (2019), “Analysis of the process of accepting nursing staff in improving the quality of health services”	Qualitative	Acceptance process according to guidelines and SOP Do not have a special committee for implementation so that the acceptance process is the responsibility of HR The method by waiting for incoming applications, mainly from nursing academics belonging to the foundation Should be more open to external recruitment	
6	Nurchahyo, Saputro & Jati (2016), “Analysis of the recruitment and selection process for the health personnel of the Healthy Archipelago Team in the Healthy Archipelago Program of the Ministry of the Republic of Indonesia”	Qualitative	Implementation of the recruitment process is guided by the legal basis The media used to get registrants still have problems because the media does not include information that affects registrants Determination of graduation is the result of psychological tests only with the agreement of the ministry of health, parties from professional organizations have not yet taken part in the graduation process	
7	Azmy (2018), “Recruitment strategy to hire the best people for organization”	Qualitative	The recruitment strategy begins with determining manpower planning which includes job design, job specifications, and job descriptions. The recruitment strategy includes recruitment sources, recruitment methods, and stages of recruitment. The positive implications of recruitment are high motivation, job satisfaction, and increased performance.	

“Literature Review: Analysis of *Soft Skills* Affecting the Recruitment Process for General Practitioners in Hospitals”

No.	Author Name, Year, Research Title	Research methods	Recruitment process	Soft skills
8	Bambuta, Mandagi & Maramis (2019), “Analysis of the recruitment of health workers at the Manado Medical Center Hospital”	Qualitative	The hospital does not yet have a reference that can be used as a target or goal Several recruitment steps can be taken to obtain more information about applicants and can more easily determine whether applicants are eligible	Always apply interviews but only discuss educational, occupational and educational background as well as hospital regulations
9	Aulia (2019), “Analysis of the implementation of recruitment and selection of prospective new employees at RSIA Kendangsari Merr Surabaya”	Qualitative	Recruitment methods consist of promotions, rotations, job placement agencies, and job training programs The selection process consists of administrative, written tests, interview tests, psychological tests, credentials, medical examinations and a work agreement for a probationary period of 3 months	
10	Oyler et al (2014), “Incorporating multiple mini-interviews in the postgraduate year 1 pharmacy residency program selection process”	Qualitative		Candidates agree that MMI enables them to communicate their abilities effectively; however, they disagreed that it was more effective than traditional interviews. All 15 interviewers completed a post-interview survey and believed that MMI effectively evaluates soft skills and that MMI is more effective than traditional interviews in assessing candidates' abilities, skills and thought processes.

A literature search obtained a total of 10 articles identified and relevant to the research objectives. The details of this research article are presented in the table above. The results of the articles obtained are explained as follows:

1. Recruitment process

Artikel discusses the recruitment process, there are 7 articles, both in terms of recruitment sources, recruitment methods, and stages in the recruitment process. For more details, see the following explanation.

a. Recruitment source

One article discusses recruitment sources. Recruitable resources that may be considered include both internal and external. Both sources of recruitment can be done according to company needs. If the company assigns internal sources, it must be ensured that the candidate already has superior knowledge, work experience, and competencies compared to external recruiting. External recruitment can be done by looking at the unavailability of candidates within the company. This should be a company's consideration in determining the availability of candidates in the labor market (Azmy, 2018).

Another article states that the method used in one hospital is an internal recruitment source. Recruitment is carried out by waiting for incoming applications, mainly from nursing academics belonging to the foundation, although it does not cover applicants who enter from outside the foundation (Suyanti, 2019).

b. Recruitment method

The recruitment method can be done online and offline. The online recruitment method requires the use of information technology to provide job vacancy information, process recruitment stages, and make recruitment decisions. Online methods are widely used by companies to expand access to information for candidates regardless of regional boundaries. The company hopes to recruit the best candidates from various countries without any regional boundaries so that they can apply the diversity of human resources. The offline method is used to obtain human resources directly by cooperating with agencies and institutions that can be used as recruitment sources (Azmi, 2018).

Likewise, another article mentions recruitment sources by using advertisements through Facebook and Instagram, then asks for help from PT companies, and thirdly sends to institutions that provide health workers according to hospital needs. Another way is through friends who come from friends who have previously worked in hospitals (Kasenger, 2017).

Likewise, another article states that the selection of participants prefers to use online. However, in practice, online publication media becomes an obstacle to the recruitment process if the participant area has internet problems (Nurcahyo et al., 2016). Recruitment methods consist of promotions, rotations, job placement agencies, and job training programs. Then there is e-recruitment through the official website, and social media advertising (Aulia, 2019).

c. Recruitment stages

The stages of recruitment must be determined by the company as part of the recruitment strategy process including screening, selection, and job placement. The screening stage aims to find out from several candidates through a job application letter, Curriculum Vitae, work experience, education level, and competency suitability for the position. This process will determine several candidates to follow the selection process. The selection stage aims to analyze the competencies and abilities of prospective employees with positions. The selection process can be determined according to the competency level requirements to carry out the job description (Azmy, 2021).

Likewise, there is one article that fully mentions the employee recruitment process. The recruitment process begins with announcing the public through social media, receiving application letters through the HRD section, conducting psychological tests, unstructured interviews, background checks, interviews about the personality of prospective health workers, and admission decisions (Kasenger, 2019).

The process of recruiting health workers begins with registration, administrative selection, psychological selection (psychological tests, FGDs, and interviews), acceptance, debriefing, and placement (Nurcahyo, 2016). Meanwhile, another article mentions that the recruitment process is carried out in full, namely having to pass the selection process consisting of administrative, written tests, interview tests, psychological tests, credentials, health checks, and work agreements for a probationary period of 3 months (Aulia, 2019).

The results of the interview in one of the articles stated that “Before, there were written exams. But now it's not done anymore. Only interviews, asking what needs to be asked then if there is a match, it will be accepted immediately” (Bambuta, 2019). The article states that the selection test conducted is only an interview test, there is no written test or psychological test. Interview tests were also only asked about the educational background and previous work background.

2. Soft skill

Soft skills needed by hospital leaders in the context of communication skills are the ability to convey information clearly. Soft skills needed in the context of attitude are honesty, loyalty, and knowledge of the field of nursing. The soft skills needed in the context of skills are being able to ensure patient safety, the ability to identify problems and the ability to plan work well (Wijayanti, 2017).

In a quantitative analysis, it is known that there is a relationship between organizational resources and service quality, which is strengthened by the existence of soft skills. Soft skills play a positive role in strengthening the relationship between organizational resources and service quality. Soft skills can support organizational resource training to improve the quality of health services (Viviyanti, 2013). This indicates that the need for soft skills in human resources makes a good

contribution to patient satisfaction but can also have a good impact on the quality of hospital services.

Companies including hospitals can determine which candidates are selected according to the competency level requirements. The candidate will then proceed to the interview and placement stage. The interview stage aims to obtain complete information related to the character, motivation, background, and abilities of the candidate. If the candidate is deemed worthy, he will proceed to the job placement process according to his position (Azmy, 2018).

Kasenger in his research based on the results of interviews "that prospective health workers must have is to have a Registration Certificate (STR) specifically for health workers". In addition, it was also stated that "the conditions must be competent, prospective health workers must also be skilled and smile."

The interview process is part of the recruitment process. The existence of soft skill problems for health workers is caused by problems found during the recruitment process interview which failed many times during the interview (Wijayanti, 2017). The interview can be conducted in an unstructured manner, then a background check is carried out, and no less important is an interview about the personality of the prospective health worker. In this case the interviewer takes part in making decisions about applicants (Kasenger, 2019).

In contrast to one article which shows that the determination of graduation is the result of a psychological test only with the agreement of the ministry of health, parties from professional organizations have not yet taken part in the graduation process (Nurcahyo et al., 2016). In the recruitment process, everyone should be involved in deciding the graduation of the participants.

In contrast to other articles, the selection test is used to identify the applicant's skills which can not only be determined in the interview process. Using various testing methods, applicants are assessed on aptitude, personality, ability, honesty and motivation. A properly designed selection test is standard, reliable, and valid in predicting applicants' success in work (Aulia, 2019).

To see whether they have soft skills or not, a lot of it is done by using the interview method. One article from the UK stated that 38 candidates were interviewed, 37 of whom completed a post-interview survey. Candidates agree that MMI enables them to convey their abilities effectively; however, they disagreed that it was more effective than traditional interviews. All 15 interviewers completed a post-interview survey and believed that MMI effectively evaluates soft skills and that MMI is more effective than traditional interviews in assessing candidates' abilities, skills, and thought processes (Oyler et al., 2014). This is different from Indonesia, which still uses conventional interviews.

IV. DISCUSSION

The results of the review above show how soft skills affect the employee recruitment process. The recruitment process consists

of a recruitment and selection process. There are still many reviews that combine the recruitment process with the selection process. Whereas in the implementation of recruitment the selection process is important to find or get employees who have good competencies. In the recruitment process, hospitals will only look at the hard skills, in contrast to the additional selection process where the hospital also considers the soft skills of applicants.

The hospital is an institution in charge of providing health services to the community. In realizing the best service quality, hospitals must be able to understand the determinants of performance and organizational survival. The quality of performance can be measured by the presence of human resources as a measure of the success of health services. It takes a way to get good human resources, one of which is through the recruitment process. This process is needed to find and find competent and qualified candidates according to their fields. Even though it seems easy, there are many things that must be considered in choosing the best job candidates.

One article explains in detail how the recruitment process and selection process for prospective new employees is. Recruitment and selection, of course, can produce new employees who not only have hard skills but also employee soft skills. As it is known that in in-hospital services, the competence of health workers will determine how to treat patients properly and correctly so that patients who seek treatment can recover. Meanwhile, soft skill competencies are also needed by every hospital health worker related to how the relationship or services provided are able to provide comfort and satisfaction to patients. However, there are still hospitals that do not carry out the stages of the recruitment process as well as possible. Such as the implementation of recruitment that does not consider the interview process and psychological tests for prospective new employees. The support and participation of the committee involved in the recruitment process will have a good impact because the assessment is not only on one point but several important points.

A. Recruitment process

1. Recruitment method

Based on the results of the articles that have been reviewed, it is known that many hospitals have implemented a recruitment process according to hospital standards and SOPs. This is supported by research by Suryanti and Nurcahyo et al., that hospitals have implemented a recruitment process in accordance with guidelines and SOPs. The guidelines used are also in accordance with the applicable legal basis (Suryanti, 2019; Nurcahyo et al., 2016). However, in the research of Bambuta et al., it is known that the hospital does not yet have a reference that can be used as a target or goal (Bambuta et al., 2019)

Based on the results of research hospitals use recruitment methods both online and online media. Online media can make it easier for applicants in any area to be able to register because of the information obtained from advertisements both on hospital website media, Facebook and Instagram. However, it

should be realized that this online media also has a weakness where areas that do not have good signal access will experience problems in the registration process.

Another method is the offline method where most hospitals use recruitment sources from internal hospitals. One review explained that hospitals prefer to conduct internal recruitment, applicants who come from academics belonging to the foundation. It is supported by the results of Kasenger's research that many applicants know information about the recruitment process from friends who have previously worked at the hospital (Kasenger, 2019). It is also supported by Suyanti's research that the method of accepting health workers by waiting for applications from the foundation's academy is a priority (Suyanti, 2019).

2. Recruitment stages

The recruitment process begins with submitting an application letter to the hospital. The file that has been submitted will be checked whether it is in accordance with the criteria required by the hospital and the file is complete. Supported by Kasenger's research (2019) that the files needed by hospitals are mandatory STR for nurses, doctors, midwives, and pharmacists, application letters, legalized transcripts, legalized diplomas, legalized transcripts, Identity Cards (KTP), Cards Family (KK), birth certificate, CV, marriage certificate if married and finally a training certificate if any.

Another study that supports Suyanti (2019) is that the criteria for health workers must pass the administrative selection. All incoming applications are screened for the completeness of the documents desired by the hospital. The administrative selection also works for reference and background checks. Based on the completeness of the proposed application file, it can be a point of consideration for the hospital because it is proof of the specifications and advantages possessed by the applicant. For example, the application is accompanied by university accreditation, work experience certificates, or important certificates from the training that has been followed that supports their expertise (Aulia, 2019).

For prospective new employees who have applied letter, they will then carry out a series of tests required by the hospital. Acceptance tests can be in the form of psychological tests, interview tests, and medical tests. Supported by research by Nurcahyo (2015) that in the selection process, applicants must go through psychological tests, both psychological written tests, FGDs, and interview tests. As stated by Aulia (2019) that the main purpose of the prospective employee test is to match a person's physical, mental and temperamental abilities with job requirements. This test is also to get to know the candidate better consisting of motivation, ambition, and future prospects.

The recruitment process is something that needs attention. The process of finding and recruiting the best-qualified candidates (from inside or outside the organization) for a new or existing job is known as the recruitment process. The recruitment process includes analyzing job requirements, attracting employees to the job, screening and selecting applicants, recruiting, and adding new employees to the

organization (Anand et al., 2018). As stated by Hasibuan's theory that recruitment is a process of withdrawal, selection, placement, orientation, and induction to get employees who are effective and efficient in helping to achieve organizational goals (Hasibuan, 2014).

In the recruitment process, of course, there are various obstacles faced that affect recruitment. Research by Afandi & Andreasta mentions recruitment problems including the lack of applicants and the lack of health workers to work (Afandi & Andreasta, 2019). The results of the review in the article by Bambuta et al., (2019) stated that the hospital did not yet have guidelines for the recruitment process. This becomes a fatal factor if the steps in the recruitment process are groundless, one of which is the lack of bias in digging up more information about applicants. In the absence of references, it will also be more difficult to determine whether the applicant is appropriate or not to join the hospital.

Another article states that the recruitment process itself requires a special implementation committee so that the recruitment process can run optimally and become the responsibility of the HR department. External recruitment methods should also be considered by hospitals so that they can be more open with external applicants (Suyanti, 2019). Another obstacle is that the interview test is conducted but only discusses the educational background, work, and education as well as hospital regulations (Bambuta et al., 2019).

B. Soft skill

Soft skills are personal and interpersonal behaviors that can develop and maximize human performance (through training, teamwork, initiative, and other decisions making). Soft skills become a person's basic capital to develop optimally according to personal personality. In order for soft skills to develop properly, it is necessary to receive continuous training so that work can be done as well as possible (Rasid et al., 2018).

Supported by research by Viviyanti (2013) soft skills play a positive role in strengthening the relationship between organizational resources and service quality. These soft skills can support organizational resource training to improve the quality of health services. Soft skills can see a person's ability to work together, solve a problem and even motivate or provide solutions to other people in a field of work. This is also reinforced by research that states that one's work performance and career success are highly dependent on the effectiveness of soft skills (Sangamitra & Priya, 2015).

Supported by the results of Wijayanti's research that the soft skills needed in the context of communication are the ability to convey information clearly, the attitude context is honesty, loyalty, and knowledge in the field of nursing. The soft skills needed in the context of skills are being able to ensure patient safety, the ability to identify problems and the ability to plan work well (Wijayanti, 2017).

In the world of health, soft skills are used to complement the hard skills possessed as an important factor in producing a quality service. The level of perfection of service quality in hospitals can be seen by the use of potential human resources in

a reasonable, effective and efficient manner in accordance with professional standards and available service standards (Viviyanti, 2013). The role of health workers in providing services in hospitals is quite important. Health workers are required to have the ability to provide health care and services, make decisions, be good communicators, lead the community and manage management. Therefore, it is not only skilled, in addition to academic ability (hard skills) but also must pay attention to abilities in several things that are inherent in a person including soft skills.

In the recruitment process, it is necessary to pay attention to both the hard skills and soft skills of the applicants. This is because the recruitment process is used to select the best candidates who can join the company. As stated by Sutrisno, recruitment aims to obtain prospective employees who allow the management to select or select candidates according to the qualifications required by the organization or company. The more candidates that are collected, the better because the possibility of getting the best candidates will be even greater (Sutrisno, 2017).

V. CONCLUSION

The article found 10 articles that discussed the recruitment process and the influence of soft skills in the recruitment process. In the recruitment process, prospective applicants go through various recruitment and selection stages. The method used by the hospital is done online and offline. Online recruitment methods are widely used in the form of information distributed via the hospital web, Facebook and Instagram, while offline recruiting internal hospitals such as recommendations from hospital employees and recruitment from foundations. Hospitals under the auspices of foundations prefer to use the offline method, namely by recruiting applicants from existing foundations, although it is possible to recruit online.

The stages of the recruitment process are carried out starting with registration and collecting the required files. At this stage, the selection of files according to the needs of the hospital is carried out by looking at the history file or applicant's competency self-data in terms of hard skills from the applicant's academic values as well as work experience and training that has been followed. The next stage is an interview test and a psychological test, but unfortunately, there are still hospitals that conduct interviews only to find out the applicant's history or background. So, this shows the hospital's lack of attention to looking at the soft skills of prospective applicants. The interview should be able to explore the personality and attitude of the applicant so that it is known the extent of the soft skills possessed.

Interviews and psychological tests are part of the selection stage, whether applicants will be able to join the hospital or not. This is also the final determination so that applicants can carry out contracts or training with hospitals. During the training period, applicants will also see how hard and soft skills they have so that they can become permanent hospital employees. These stages, if done properly by the hospital, can help the hospital to get professional health workers.

Soft skills are now also one of the competencies expected by all health workers who join hospitals. The soft skill needs of health workers in hospitals include clear communication skills, and the ability to be honest and loyal to the hospital. Self-development of health workers is also needed so that it will support skills that are able to ensure patient safety. The ability to make decisions and good job planning is also needed in contributing high soft skills.

The existence of psychological tests and interview tests in the recruitment and selection process will be able to see how the interpersonal skills of prospective applicants in carrying out their work later. One of the overseas hospitals has used an interview instrument to identify or see how the soft skills of applicants are so that they are able to have competent health workers.

REFERENCES

1. Anand, D. V. V., Shanthanlakshmi, D. M., Srinivasan, D. G. U., Arunkumar, V., Icwarya, G., Nandhu, S., & Kamatchi, S. M. (2018). A Study on Effectiveness of Recruitment Organizational Support in Ites. *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics*, 119(7), 10.
2. Arifandi, A., & Meliala, A. (2017). Factors Affecting the Recruitment of Doctors at the Health Center in the Work Area of the Buol District Health Office in 2016. *Jurnal Kebijakan Kesehatan Indonesia*, 6(3), 103. <https://doi.org/10.22146/jkki.v6i3.29659>
3. Anand, D. V. V., Shanthanlakshmi, D. M., Srinivasan, D. G. U., Arunkumar, V., Icwarya, G., Nandhu, S., & Kamatchi, S. M. (2018). A Study on Effectiveness of Recruitment Organizational Support in Ites. *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics*, 119(7), 10.
4. Azwar, V. (2013). The Moderation Role of Soft Skills in Improving the Quality of Hospital Services. *Jurnal Kesehatan Masyarakat Nasional*, 7(8).
5. Azmy, A. (2018). Recruitment strategy to hire the best people for organization. *Jurnal of Management and Leadership*. 1(2).
6. Aulia, A. F. (2019). Analysis of the implementation of recruitment and selection of prospective new employees at RSIA Kendangsari Merr Surabaya. *MTPH Journa*. 3(2).
7. Bambuta, R. M., Mandagi, C. K. F., & Maramis, F. R. (2019) Analysis of the recruitment of health workers at the Manado Medical Center Hospital. *Jurnal KESMAS*. 8(3).
8. Hasibuan, Malayu SP. (2014). Human Resource Management, Fourteenth Edition, Jakarta, Publisher: Bumi Aksara.
9. Nurcahyo. (2016). Analysis of the Recruitment and Selection Process for Health Personnel of the Healthy Nusantara Team in the Healthy Nusantara Program of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia.

JURNAL KESEHATAN MASYARAKAT (e-Journal),
4(4).

10. Oyler, D. R., Cook, A., & Bush, H. (2014). Incorporating multiple mini-interviews in the postgraduate year 1 pharmacy residency program selection process. *Am J Health-Syst Pharm*. Vol 71.
11. Rasid, Z., Tewal, B., & Kojo, C. (2018). The Influence of Hard Skills and Soft Skills on Employee Performance at Perum Damri Manado. *Jurnal EMBA: Jurnal Riset Ekonomi, Manajemen, Bisnis dan Akuntansi*, 6(2), Article 2. <https://doi.org/10.35794/emba.v6i2.20030>
12. Suryani, P. (2019). *Effect of Recruitment Process, Employee Placement and Compensation on Employee Performance at BNI Syariah Banda Aceh Branch Office [Underthesis]*. Universitas Islam Negeri Ar-Raniry.
13. Sutrisno, E. (2017). *Human Resource Management*. Kencana Publisher.
14. Suryanti, H. (2019). Analysis of the nursing staff recruitment process in improving the quality of health services. *Jurnal Ilmiah Kesehatan*. 18(1).
15. Wijayanti, M. E., Wardani, Y., & Ujiningtyas, S. H. (2017). Health Service Needs on Soft Skills Graduates of Third Diploma Nursing in Indonesia. *Jurnal Keperawatan Sriwijaya*, 4(2355), 12.